

JURIDICAL SCIENCES

THEORETICAL ASPECTS OF THE LEGAL CAPACITY OF A LEGAL ENTITY

Tsereteli G.

Doctoral Student of Caucasus's International University

Abstract

The relevance of the presented article is determined by the legal and factual circumstances that the criminal liability of a legal entity is provided for in numerous international conventions and also in the domestic legislation of many countries. In Georgian legislation, specifically through the amendments made to the Criminal Code of Georgia on August 25, 2006, the issue of the punishability of a legal entity was legalized. This has led to diverse approaches regarding how a legal entity could commit a crime when, generally, only a natural person can be the subject of a crime. The question also arose that, in fact, a legal entity could not commit a crime without the assistance of a natural person. It is precisely here that the problem emerged: whether the issue of indirect liability of the legal entity arises in the process of committing a criminal act, or whether the legal entity is being punished for a criminal act committed by another. Furthermore, the problem significantly emerges whether legal entities should be considered as subjects equal to natural persons in legal relations. The aim of the article is to analyze the issues raised during the research process and to highlight the peculiarities of the criminal liability of a legal entity.

To address the problems raised in **the article, the methodological basis of the research** includes historical, formal-logical, comparative-legal, and other methods.

Keywords: Legal entity, natural person, state, direct liability, indirect liability, crime, precedent, tradition, subject, right, will, theory, property.

Introduction

At the modern stage, it became necessary to legally justify the existence of a legal entity, since along with the development of legal relations in society, the process of forming legal entities, or more precisely, collective associations, began.

It is known in world history that the most developed legal culture in the field of civil law existed in the Roman Empire. Specifically, even Roman jurists compared organizations to natural persons and stated that an organization acts instead of a natural person, in its form, with the status of a separate person, which is also evident in the origins of the 'fiction theory' that emerged in the Middle Ages and became particularly prominent in the legal theory of foreign countries. Individual examples of these subjects are found in the following sources: treasury, municipia, various associations of persons of a common profession. In Rome, the legal personality of a legal entity was considered in different contexts than at the modern stage; for example, a legal entity had the right of patronage, which was almost familial in nature and, with a few exceptions, was not considered legally capable; it also had the right to receive inherited property. As for the creation of a legal entity, in this regard, based on the laws of the 12 Tables, there was almost complete freedom to form collegia, associations, and other types of societies, which could define any matter for their associations by statute, provided that the law was not violated. According to Gaius, this legislative order regarding the freedom to create collegia was adopted from Solon, i.e., from Greek legislation.

One of the earliest definitions regarding a legal entity is considered to be that of Pope Innocent IV in 1245: "A legal entity exists only in the form of a fiction. It has not been granted a body, meaning it does not possess

will. Only the members can act, not the corporation, since a corporation, for example, cannot commit a crime."

The first scientific study of the legal entity was carried out by Savigny (1840), the founder of the historical school of law, and it became known as the 'fiction theory'. In other words, the 'personification theory', which had a great influence on subsequent scientific research and still exists today in various modifications. The essence of this theory is that will, consciousness, i.e., the qualities of a legal subject, belong only to a human, a separate individual. However, to achieve a number of necessary goals that are impossible for an individual person to implement, institutions and corporations must be created, to which the legislator, through their personification, grants the qualities of a person (subject), inasmuch as rights are inconceivable without subjects. Savigny seeks a solution in fiction, in the creation of an artificial subject, such that in reality, the subject can only be a human, while the so-called legal entity is fictitious. Many opinions were expressed against this theory. Germanists (H. Beseler, O. Gierke), as well as numerous Romanists (F. Regelsberger), relying on German national law, argue that the legal entity is not a fiction at all, but a real, acting subject, which, despite not being a natural person, is just as much a subject of law as the latter, and not merely similar to it. Followers of this theory consider the legal personality of a legal entity to be as real as that of a natural person. Brinz's attitude towards the legal entity is interesting. He considers it as a 'garden scarecrow', not even worth paying attention to. In his opinion, law belongs not to someone, but to something, specifically to the purposes for which the property of the so-called legal entity is intended. According to this doctrine, a legal entity is a continuous state of property management. This theory faced criticism, arguing that a subjective right cannot

exist without a subject, which in turn can only be a human, because objective law regulates relationships between people. Furthermore, the followers of this theory cannot bypass the fiction theory, inasmuch as the attribution of purposes is nothing but fiction.

In scientific circles, a special place is occupied by the concept of the existence of a legal entity as a real subject in a real society – the 'social organism' theory, which spread in Germany (H. Beseler, O. Gierke, H. Dernburg, F. Regelsberger) and France (L. Michoud, R. Saleilles). Representatives of this theory consider it a mistake that only natural persons can be subjects of legal relations. In their understanding, alongside individual subjects of law, there also exists a supra-individual organism. Thus, O. Gierke, the founder of the 'organic theory', argued that a legal entity is a special corporeal-social organism, an associative personality. It is not a product of the legal order, but a real, essential organism influenced by the state. The distinguishing features of this entity are will, attitude, interests, and vital activity. In other words, this theory proceeds from the premise that every 'collectivity' that meets all important conditions constitutes a legal entity. Any legal entity needs will to exercise its rights, since where there is no will, there is no right. However, real will exists with humans, therefore an individual can express the collective will, and this is possible if the latter has appropriate organs¹.

The Need for Criminal Liability of Legal Entities

During the research for the article, the problem emerged regarding the extent to which it is possible for a legal entity to be held criminally liable for crimes committed within its sphere of activity. It should be noted that until the mid-19th century, this problem was viewed negatively. Concurrently, an opposing opinion developed with substantiated arguments: "that this was an attempt by the state to tighten control over the negative consequences of the activities of large corporations"².

Despite numerous objections, the legal entity has nevertheless established itself in law generally as a subject, and primarily as a subject of private law, which was a logical consequence of the development and expansion of the circle of civil legal relations. In any country's legal system, a legal entity stands alongside a natural person as a subject of law, meaning it possesses legal rights and obligations, property, and identification data. Given that a legal entity is actively involved in various types of legal relations (civil, administrative), over time, willingly or unwillingly, it also came under the purview of criminal law. Legal science began to explore whether a legal entity could be a subject of criminal law against the backdrop of the fundamental principles of the criminal law field, which at first glance seem completely incompatible with a legal entity: personal responsibility, individualization of punishment. These principles are essentially unchanged in any country's legal system and form the basis of criminal law.

Precisely against this background, the legal fiction still constitutes a subject of criminal law, commits crimes, and is punished. Its capacity as a subject of criminal law is fully demonstrated in Anglo-American legal systems, although it is also gradually gaining a firm foothold in Roman law system countries. It has its peculiarities. Given that it differs qualitatively from a natural person, criminal law considers it from a different perspective as a subject of criminal law.

Indirect criminal liability

When considering a legal entity in the context of criminal law, we cannot overlook the institution of indirect liability established in Anglo-American legal systems (United States, England).

Indirect liability is the most convenient formula used in the criminal law of England and the USA for the liability of certain types of legal entities, such as business entities, among which the most common type is the corporation.

The institution of indirect liability originated within tort law, the essence of which is that the employer is responsible for any action carried out by the employee within the scope of their employment³. This doctrine was developed in the 17th century and was justified by the fact that since the employer benefited from the employee's activities, the employer should also bear the burden of the damage⁴. However, in criminal law, indirect liability differs slightly from its civil law understanding. To illustrate, let's consider a significant civil case: *Lloyd v Grace, Smith & Co*. The case was as follows: In a solicitor's office, a clerk, independently of his employer, persuaded a widow to give him power of attorney to sell specific property, handed over the property ownership documents to him, and had her sign two documents without reading them to her or explaining their legal significance and possible consequences. The widow believed this was a necessary condition for selling the property. In reality, the documents were deeds transferring the property to the clerk. The clerk dishonestly sold this property cheaply for his own purposes to benefit himself. Later, during the court hearing, it was considered that since the clerk committed this violation while exercising his authority, his employer was responsible for it. If we consider this from a criminal law perspective, the picture emerges as follows: since civil liability was imposed on the employer for the damage caused by the clerk, then with this approach, it would not be surprising if criminal liability were also imposed on him, specifically for the theft of property ownership documents and the fraudulent appropriation of funds. However, it is self-evident that the employer could not be held criminally liable for the same act for which he incurred civil liability. The employer is responsible for the tort, which in criminal law constitutes theft of documents, fraud, or any other crime that causes civil damage, but in none of these cases can the employer be held responsible for committing the crime solely on the grounds that the employee hired by him acted within

¹ P. V. Aleksey, D. A. Kondakov. The Problem of the Legal Entity in Civil Law Literature. Journal "Zakon i Pravo" [Law and Right], 2003. No. 5.

² See J. Pradel: Comparative Criminal Law, Georgian translation, ed. T. Ninidze, 1999, p. 88.

³ John Smith, Brian Hogan. Criminal Law. London, Edinburgh, Dublin, 1996. p. 174

⁴ Gerry Ferguson. Corruption and Criminal Liability. P. 4. Available on the website: www.iccr.law.abc.ca/Publications/Reports/CorporateCriminal.pdf

the scope of the activities defined for him by the employer⁵.

In cases of indirect criminal liability, the following circumstances must be established:

1. The crime must have been committed by an employee hired by the company within the scope of the activities assigned to them by the company.

2. The criminal act must have been carried out in the name of the company and for its benefit, if not fully, then at least partially.

3. The criminal act carried out by the employee must have been openly or covertly inspired by the company's management, which directs the company's activities, or it must have been approved after the act was carried out.

Unfortunately or fortunately, courts in England and the United States do not always strictly adhere to this requirement.

In the common law family, two groups of crimes are distinguished: 1. Traditional crimes, which are inherently crimes without additional legislative intervention and developed within Common Law, and 2. Crimes of legislative origin – so-called statutory crimes, which are prohibited by specific legislative acts and are enforced by the threat of punishment. Statutory crimes, in turn, comprise two groups: 1. Crimes that do not include *mens rea*⁶ as a mandatory element and are limited to establishing *actus reus*⁷, and 2. Crimes that consider *mens rea* as a mandatory element along with *actus reus*. The first type of crime is called strict liability offenses⁸. Furthermore, some authors refer to them as absolute prohibition offenses, especially judges in their decisions⁹.

Indirect criminal liability applies to all groups of crimes discussed, and it is particularly convenient for strict liability offenses, since, as noted, it is not mandatory to investigate subjective elements when committing crimes in this category. As for other statutory crimes and traditional crimes, the scope of application is more or less limited.

Based on the above, two types of indirect criminal liability can be distinguished: indirect strict criminal liability (hereinafter objective indirect criminal liability) and indirect subjective criminal liability.

As mentioned above, there is a group of crimes in common law countries known as strict liability offenses. These crimes are scattered across various levels of legislative acts adopted by the relevant territorial legislative body. Their establishment is limited solely to *actus reus*. However, it should also be noted that although such crimes are mostly of statutory origin, there are also several such crimes in common law, for example: public nuisance, criminal libel, and contempt of court¹⁰. When framed within indirect liability, it must be determined whether this prohibited act was carried

out by 1. an employee of the legal entity, 2. whether this occurred within the scope of the activities assigned to them. As for the 3rd element – open or covert inspiration of the act by the legal entity – it is not mandatory. Also, it is not necessary to ascertain whether the offender carried out this act for the benefit of the legal entity or in its interests. This element points to characteristics typical of the subjective aspect, and its non-consideration is logical given that we have termed the issue under discussion objective liability.

The Medicines Act 1968 of England provides that any person is prohibited from the retail sale of medicinal products of a specific content unless there is a prescription from an appropriate medical professional. In the case: *Pharmaceutic Society of Great Britain v. Storkwain Ltd.*, the company dispensed a specific medicine based on a prescription bearing a doctor's signature. It was later determined that the prescription was forged. The forgery was so convincing that the pharmacists were deceived without difficulty, despite having verified the authenticity of the prescription. The House of Lords considered that one of the Queen's Bench courts was correct when it recommended conviction to the magistrate judge¹¹. Thus, the strict liability of a person seems very simple, as proving their culpability is not necessary, and an act carried out in the name of the company by its employee within the scope of activities assigned to them by the company is already sufficient for criminal liability to arise for this company.

Some authors do not consider strict liability offences to be real crimes. In the case: *Wings Ltd v. Ellis*, Lord Scarman considers that the Trade Descriptions Act 1968, which defines a range of offences in the field of consumer protection, does not contain true crimes. Its purpose is not the implementation of criminal objectives, but the protection of trade standards.

For statutory offences, the company's liability arises indirectly, however, it is interesting for which specific natural person's action it is held liable – that of a managing official, or an ordinary employee who has no mechanism for decision-making and directing the company's activities. The view that an act committed by an employee of any level within the scope of the company's activities is perceived as the company's crime is not entirely substantiated, as another hypothesis has emerged, suggesting that only the action of a leading official is considered the company's action.

We have seen that for indirect strict liability, a company (legal entity) is liable if: 1. The offence is committed by an employee of the company; 2. The offence is committed in the name of the company, within the scope of its activities. Furthermore, in the case of this type of liability, the direct perpetrator of the violation is an ordinary employee of the company. Also, strict liability, as we saw from the example, does not

⁵ Smith, Hogan. *Criminal Law...* p. 175

⁶ Note: *Mens rea* is a Latin phrase meaning "guilty mind". Today, in legal terms, it refers to a mental state that includes intent, knowledge of the essence of crime, and other subjective elements that constitute qualifying circumstances of a specific crime (*English-Georgian Legal Explanatory Dictionary*, Tbilisi: 2004. p. 365)

⁷ Note: *Actus reus* is a Latin phrase meaning criminal act. Today in legal terms it means an incriminated act that is expressed through action and inaction (*English-Georgian Legal Explanatory Dictionary*, Tbilisi: 2004. p. 20)

⁸ See below for more details on these issues

⁹ Smith, Hogan. *Criminal Law...* p.101

¹⁰ Gerry Ferguson. *Corruption and Criminal Liability...* P.4.

¹¹ Smith, Hogan. *Criminal Law...* p.101

require the establishment of the subjective element of the crime. Establishing the two components mentioned above and the act prohibited by law (action or inaction) is relevant. Here the question must be raised, whether all statutory offences of strict liability are punishable in all cases, or if there are any circumstances excluding liability? For example, can a company be exempted from liability if it is proven that it made every effort to ensure that the offence did not occur, but due to the incompetence of its ordinary employee, despite strict preventive measures taken within the company, the violation still happened? To clarify this issue, the nature of the strict liability offence itself must be ascertained.

Although we have placed strict liability offences within an objective framework, this does not mean that there is no way back, i.e., it does not mean that the objective commission of the act will a priori lead to liability. The fact is that there is a confusion of terms: absolute liability is incorrect, and strict liability is correct, because if we considered it otherwise, no defendant could escape criminal liability. Nevertheless, courts still use this term [absolute liability], which is not appropriate¹². That is, as mentioned, there is a way back – circumstances excluding liability, in the presence of which a legal entity is exempted from indirect strict criminal liability.

Traditional grounds. It is difficult to talk about circumstances excluding strict indirect liability inasmuch as circumstances excluding liability inherently involve a subjective element, while strict liability is more or less based on objective circumstances. Despite this, we cannot bypass it; it is still encountered in practice, although it is characterized by a very high degree of individuality – it depends on the specifics of the particular case. It is possible that in one case a specific circumstance excludes liability, but in another case, the same circumstance may not be considered as such. This depends on multiple factors.

Generally, in criminal law, circumstances excluding liability are based on two grounds: 1. Justificatory and 2. Excusatory. The first excludes the act, while the second excludes blaming the person. In the case of indirect strict liability, and particularly in relation to a legal entity, only justificatory circumstances, which rely on objective factors, are relevant. But if we consider it this way, it turns out that excusatory defenses such as mental disorder, minority, duress, intoxication, and others are rejected¹³. This assumption might be irrelevant in relation to the indirect criminal liability of a natural person, as it is entirely possible that these could apply to them and they could be exempted from liability (since the issue of natural persons is not the subject of discussion in this work, we will not dwell on it), but in relation to a legal entity, this is less permissible. Specifically, it is unlikely and almost excluded that a company would be exempted from indirect strict liability for a violation of any legislative act by a natural person on the grounds that this person was experiencing a moment of mental disorder. In this case, this person might be exempted from liability, but the company will be held liable because it did not take appropriate measures

that would have prevented the violation. Also, if we assume that a company employee was undergoing a mental disorder, or was in another state of non-imputability, for example, when they made an excusable mistake, this excludes the liability of this specific employee, but not that of the company, even with the argument that it failed to properly select service personnel in such a way that a subsequent violation would not occur.

Thus, among the traditional grounds excluding indirect strict criminal liability, only justificatory circumstances exist for a company, while excusatory circumstances are irrelevant to it.

Specific grounds. There are specific circumstances excluding liability, which represent an independent branch from traditional circumstances and apply during indirect strict criminal liability. This is a circumstance excluding blame, i.e., an excusatory circumstance, called due diligence, which means that the subject has taken all necessary measures for the prevention of the crime, but despite these necessary measures, the criminal act still occurs. In judicial practice, equal importance is often not given to this circumstance. Mainly, its acceptance by the court as a circumstance excluding liability occurs when the statute itself provides for it as such, or in another case, when its use in favor of the defendant is linked to the legislator's intent.

Statutes imposing strict liability rarely provide for due diligence measures. One example is the UK's Food Safety Act 1990, where most offenses are subject to strict liability, while Section 21(1) provides that any person charged with an offense under this Act shall be acquitted if they prove that they took all reasonable precautions and exercised all due diligence to avoid the commission of the offense by themselves or by a person under their control. However, if this defense involves an allegation that the commission of the offense was due to the act or default of another person, the defendant must provide the prosecution with written information identifying that other person¹⁴. The norms established by this Act concern the prohibition of selling food that contravenes established safety standards, does not meet the required quality, contains an incorrect description of the food's composition, or its presentation misleads the consumer. Specifically, Sections 21(3) and 21(4) state: 3. A person shall be acquitted if they prove that a) the commission of the offense was due to the act or default of another person, not being a person under their control, or to reliance on information supplied by such a person; b) they carried out all such checks of the food in question as were reasonable in all the circumstances, or it was reasonable in all the circumstances for them to rely on checks carried out by the person who supplied the food to them; and c) they did not know and had no reason to suspect at the time of the commission of the alleged offense that their act or omission would amount to an offense. 4. A person shall be acquitted if they prove that a) the commission of the offense was due to the act or default of another person who was not under their control, or due to information supplied to them by such a person; b) the sale,

¹² Clarkson, Keating, *Criminal Law...* p. 207

¹³ Clarkson, Keating, *Criminal Law...* p. 208

¹⁴ Smith, Hogan, *Criminal Law...* p.122

or intended sale, which constitutes the offense, was not under their name or mark; and c) they did not know, and could not reasonably have been expected to know at the time the offense was committed, that their act or omission constituted an offense¹⁵.

So, for example, if a shop owner sells a candy containing a foreign object, such as a piece of a nail, and is charged with selling food of unsatisfactory quality and composition, the requirements for which are provided in Section 14 of the Food Safety Act 1990, they must convince the court that they took all possible precautions. Since this defense mechanism requires that the offense be caused by the act or default of another person, who in this case would be the candy manufacturer, the shop owner must bring this to the prosecutor's attention. The court may then rely on paragraph 4 mentioned above, and if the circumstances of the case satisfy all the requirements specified therein, the defense will be successful. Although the requirements set out in the law may seem difficult to implement in practice at first glance, in this particular case, we see that it is not so difficult: a) Someone not under the shop owner's control is responsible for the presence of the foreign object in the candy, and it is clear that the shop owner is not required to identify this person. b) No one really expects a shop owner, who merely sells the candy, to open it and check its contents as a measure of due diligence, and c) If the manufacturer has a good reputation and their business history does not contain any illegal actions, the shop owner has no reason to suspect the existence of a criminal act, specifically that the candy they sold contains a foreign object. There may be other circumstances under which satisfying the conditions necessary for the defense mechanism is not so easy, but the defendant can convince the court in other ways that, based on the totality of the factual circumstances, they took all reasonable measures and exercised due diligence¹⁶.

This defense mechanism, defined in statutes, sometimes does not represent a complex chain of conditions at all, although in all cases it requires proof of two components: 1. There was no mens rea in their conduct, and 2. They exercised due diligence. Such an approach is a significant step forward for the institution of strict liability and further convinces us that it is not liability for absolute prohibition; consequently, the term 'objective liability' is only a conditional heading, as it is not reflected in its full meaning. Nevertheless, there are still gaps that need to be filled¹⁷.

The due diligence defense mechanism is not used very often in judicial practice and, apart from the two factors mentioned above (1. when the statute directly provides for it as such, or 2. when its use is the legislator's intention for the benefit of the defendant), it also depends on the court's discretion. In practice, there are frequent cases where, despite a company's full compliance with due diligence norms, it is still subject to criminal liability. For example, let's take one of the high-

profile and problematic cases in US judicial practice concerning the indictment of a major film production corporation - United States v. Twentieth Century Fox Films Corp¹⁸. In 1951, the company Twentieth Century Fox Films Corp (hereinafter 'Fox') entered into an agreement with the federal government, according to which it would refrain from monopolizing film products and would not force cinemas to obtain several licenses simultaneously to screen films when their desire was to obtain only one license. Thirty years after this agreement was made, 'Fox' was convicted of violating its terms, based on the actions of a branch manager, Lila Goldstein. Despite convincing the court that it had made every possible effort to ensure its employees did not violate the agreement, the court still did not consider this circumstance as excluding liability. All company employees who were questioned at the court hearing, including Goldstein, confirmed the fact that they had signed the aforementioned agreement prohibiting violation and took an oath to comply with it. The court did not accept any of this evidence as a circumstance excluding liability. It convicted the company for violating this agreement solely due to the actions of one branch manager, despite the latter proving at the court hearing the existence of a whole range of due diligence measures taken by them, which had been in place for several decades. The court imposed liability on 'Fox' based on the principle of vicarious liability - 'A corporation is criminally liable for the actions of its employee if they act on behalf of the company and within the scope of their employment', imposed a fine as punishment: 50,000 US dollars and ordered payment of court costs amounting to 40,397 US dollars¹⁹. The appellate court upheld the decision of the first instance court, considering that the conviction was carried out in full compliance with the principle of vicarious criminal liability. However, the Supreme Court later rejected the appellate court's reasoning and noted that the due diligence measures implemented by the company must necessarily be taken into account during its conviction process²⁰. Despite such recommendations, courts still apply strict approaches.

The standard of due diligence is also discussed in the US Model Penal Code. Specifically, Article 8C2.5-e distinguishes: An "effective program to prevent and detect violations of law" means a program that has been reasonably designed, implemented, and enforced so that it generally will be effective in preventing and detecting criminal conduct. Failure to prevent or detect the instant offense, by itself, does not mean that the program was not effective. The hallmark of an effective program to prevent and detect violations of law is that the organization exercised due diligence in seeking to prevent and detect criminal conduct. Due diligence requires at a minimum that the organization must have taken the following seven steps: 1) The organization must have established compliance standards and proce-

¹⁵ Ibid. p.123

¹⁶ Ibid. p.124

¹⁷ Ibid. p.127

¹⁸ Andrew Weissman, Richard Ziegler, Luke McLoughlin & Joseph McFadden. Reforming Corporate Criminal Liability

to Promote Responsible Corporate Behaviour. U.S. Chamber for Legal Reform, 2008. p.11. Available on the website: www.InstituteForLegalReform.com

¹⁹ Ibid.

²⁰ Ibid.

dures that are reasonably capable of reducing the prospect of criminal conduct and which must be followed by its employees. 2) High-level personnel of the organization must have been assigned overall responsibility to oversee compliance of personnel activities with the established preventive standards and procedures. 3) The organization must have taken due care not to delegate substantial discretionary authority to individuals whom the organization knew, or should have known through the exercise of due diligence, had a propensity to engage in illegal activities. 4) The organization must have taken steps to communicate effectively its standards and procedures developed for preventive purposes to its employees: by disseminating publications within the company, conducting their training, or providing them with information in another reasonable form. 5) The organization must take steps to comply with the standards it has developed: it must arrange monitoring and auditing systems in such a way that the detection of crime becomes possible through the response of the employees themselves, which also includes ensuring the safety of the whistleblower. 6) Crime prevention mechanisms must include an adequate disciplinary system, which includes employee responsibility even when they knew about the crime and did not respond appropriately. Adequate response towards employees who are responsible for the activities of other employees is a necessary component of ensuring prevention. However, whether the disciplinary measures taken are appropriate should be assessed individually based on the specifics of the particular case. 7) After an offense has been detected, the company must take appropriate measures in response to it and for the purpose of subsequent correction of the crime, which is expressed in changing the existing preventive mechanisms for improvement²¹. These measures, which imply the exercise of due diligence by the organization, are interesting for the issue, and the court is not obliged to use them.

The term "organization" used in this article refers not only to business entities, but also includes non-profit legal entities and associations that are not legal entities. That is, the word "organization" gives us grounds to conclude that liability applies to both non-profit and for-profit legal entities.

It follows from court decisions that the court itself decides independently, based on expediency, whether to apply indirect strict liability towards a legal entity, inasmuch as in strict liability offenses, which are mainly provided for by statute, the disposition of the act does not specifically establish whether the liability should be strict or not. The legislator entrusts this decision to the court; consequently, it also entrusts to the court whether to consider a particular circumstance as grounds for excluding liability when the law itself does not provide for such circumstances.

Let's consider another case where a company was held criminally liable for an act committed through negligence. At first glance, it seems very strange to declare a legal entity responsible and punish it for this crime, especially with such a severe measure of responsibility. The case was as follows: In Pennsylvania, on

April 3, 1978, a school bus belonging to the company McIlwain SchoolBus Lines, Inc and driven by one of the company's hired employees, hit a six-year-old girl, Lori Sharp. When the girl got off the bus, as the bus started moving, the driver did not notice her presence there and hit her. On May 26, 1978, the court found the corporation guilty of vehicular homicide. The decision was appealed by the defense on the grounds that the said crime could only be committed by a natural person and in no case by a corporation. Section 3732 of the Vehicle Code provides: "The death of any person caused recklessly or with gross negligence by any person, where such death is the result of a violation of any law or ordinance concerning the operation or use of a vehicle or the regulation of traffic, constitutes a crime. The corporation argued its case before the authorities, who responded as follows: Sections 4551 and 4552 of the Pennsylvania Vehicle Code authorize the Department of Transportation to establish regulations concerning the equipment of school buses. These regulations require that the bus have a mirror on the driver's right side to allow for a clear view of potential hazards. This requirement was not met by the company. Also, a mirror should be installed allowing the driver, seated on the left, a proper view. This requirement was also not properly fulfilled by the company, preventing the driver from having a proper view of the side. These violations are punishable under Section 4551 by a fine of 50 to 100 dollars. Furthermore, the local authorities explained that although Section 3732 does not explicitly use the term 'corporation', the term 'person' used therein includes corporations as well, and further specification is not necessary²². This case clearly shows that the company did not comply with the legislative requirements regarding transport safety, which subsequently led to the death of the six-year-old child. Had the company complied with all the regulations, it could have argued its intent to comply before the court; however, the girl's death resulted from its negligence. If the court had not found the company culpable, it would have avoided criminal liability.

This case is also interesting from another perspective. The issue of the company's liability arose, despite the fact that the regulations did not explicitly provide for the criminal liability of companies. The court reasoned that, despite this, the regulation also applied to legal entities and directly led to the imposition of a fine as the penalty, although Section 3732 along with deprivation, because a fine, unlike the named types of punishment, can quite possibly be imposed on a legal entity as a form of criminal liability²³. I.e., under the conditions of this case, there was a basis for objective liability, as it is based on objective circumstances; specifically, in this case, a causal chain is present. The responsible party is the one whose action caused the criminal outcome; at this moment, it is the company. Had it maintained the vehicle's mirrors properly, there would have been no victim. Consequently, the company itself is responsible.

The liability turned out to be objective, i.e., strict, but this still does not give us grounds to say that it was

²¹ Kaplan, Weisberg, Binder. Criminal Law: Cases and Materials. New York. 2004. p. 832

²² Kaplan, Weisberg, Binder. Criminal Law... p. 837

²³ Ibid. pp. 838-839

absolute, because upon determination, given the existence of legal prerequisites (taking appropriate precautionary measures), it could be released from liability. Furthermore, we also saw that if indirect liability arises, full responsibility rests entirely with the legal entity, in this case, the company. The main features of indirect objective liability concerning a legal entity are as follows:

1. The action must be carried out by a hired employee,
2. The action must arise from the company's activities.
3. There must be a causal link between the action and the result concerning material offenses, whereas this link is not required for formal offenses.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that, according to some researchers, the criminal liability of a legal entity was nevertheless artificially introduced and took its place in the development of criminal law, becoming almost equal to a natural person in its subjectivity. This was manifested by the fact that it was brought within the framework of criminal law, which is fundamentally based on crime prevention.

We can unequivocally answer the research problem positively, since indeed a legal entity can be punished for the antisocial actions of another, to which certain characteristics have been artificially attributed, the commission of which is only possible by a natural person, which was clearly revealed during the research process presented in the article.

At the modern stage, the scope of liability of a legal entity in criminal law has expanded, which has covered a large area of crimes in this regard, such as, for example, the deprivation of human life, etc.

In Georgian legislation at the modern stage, presenting a legal entity as a subject of criminal law is not particularly relevant, which requires fundamental research in this direction in the context of the practices of other countries.

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